

Determination of 2-Hydroxy-5-methyldibenzoylmethane in Non-aqueous Medium by Enthalpimetric, Conductometric and Potentiometric Methods

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Pyrazolines and their different substituted derivatives are widely used in medicinal chemistry¹. Literature survey reveals that no non-aqueous titrimetric method has been suggested for the determination of 2-hydroxy-5-methyldibenzoylmethane (HMDM) so far. Therefore, in the present communication these methods have been used for its determination.

Results and Discussion

Enthalpimetric titration curves show sudden rise in temperature at the end-point. Titration curves for conductometric titration did not show sharp break but the end point could be determined by extrapolation. Potentiometric titration curves show sharp rise in potential at the end-point and percentage error in estimation is minimum. Comparison of the results (Table 1) obtained by three different methods for *t*-Bu₄NOH and alcoholic KOH shows that alcoholic KOH is the most suitable titrant for estimation of HMDM. It is observed from

Table 1 that HMDM can be quantitatively estimated between 1.0 and 15.0 mg by enthalpimetric titration. Conductometric titration also gave good results for 1.0–45.0 mg of HMDM but the percentage errors were relatively large. Potentiometric titration was found to yield best result amongst the three methods. Error in the estimation was found to be minimum (usually less than $\pm 1.0\%$) and the method can estimate 1.0–50.0 mg HMDM accurately under the experimental conditions.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade, and wherever necessary purified further employing standard methods. HMDM was synthesised by the known methods² and the purity of the compound was tested by its melting point (90°) and molecular weight (254). All solvents were made anhydrous by known methods³.

A 0.1 M tetra-*n*-butyl ammonium hydroxide (*t*-Bu₄NOH) in toluene-methanol solution was diluted

TABLE 1—TITRATIONS OF HMDM WITH ALCOHOLIC KOH AND *t*-Bu₄NOH

Wt. titrated mg	Enthalpimetry		Conductometry		Potentiometry	
	Wt. found mg	Error %	Wt. found mg	Error %	Wt. found mg	Error %
<i>Titration with t-Bu₄NOH</i>						
1.270	1.234 1	-2.8	1.234 4	-2.79	1.250 1	-1.5
2.540	2.480 1	-2.1	2.514 6	-1.0	2.514 6	-1.0
5.080	5.010 1	-1.3	5.028 1	-1.1	5.113 1	+0.66
10.160	10.011 1	-1.4	10.205 7	+0.39	10.210 1	+0.49
15.240	15.011 3	-1.5	15.180 1	-0.39	15.208 1	-0.26
20.320	19.811 2	-2.4	20.031 1	-1.3	20.570 1	+1.2
25.400	25.899 8	+1.9	25.630 1	+0.9	25.708 1	+1.1
30.480	29.552 1	-3.0	30.861 0	+1.2	30.451 2	-0.09
35.560	34.512 3	-2.9	35.201 2	-1.0	35.301 3	-0.73
40.640	39.014 5	-3.9	40.233 6	-1.01	40.311 3	-0.81
45.720	43.462 5	-4.9	45.064 4	-1.4	45.301 2	-0.91
50.800	47.767 2	-5.9	49.762 1	-2.0	50.214 3	-1.1
<i>Titration with alcoholic KOH</i>						
1.270	1.332 1	-2.9	1.240 1	-2.3	1.255 1	-1.17
2.540	2.490 1	-1.9	2.520 2	-0.77	2.510 2	-1.17
5.080	5.021 1	-1.1	5.031 2	-0.98	5.030 1	-0.98
10.160	10.051 1	-1.0	10.058 4	-1.0	10.181 1	+0.2
15.240	15.024 1	-1.4	15.062 4	-1.1	15.141 2	-0.65
20.320	19.840 1	-2.3	20.262 7	-0.2	20.260 1	-0.2
25.400	25.812 3	+1.6	25.894 5	+1.9	25.510 2	+0.43
30.480	29.654 3	-2.7	30.401 2	-0.2	30.451 2	-0.09
35.560	34.591 2	-2.7	35.201 2	-1.0	35.360 2	-0.59
40.640	39.101 9	-3.7	40.411 4	-0.5	40.280 1	-0.88
45.720	43.854 6	-4.0	45.872 4	+0.8	45.301 2	-0.9
50.800	48.011 2	-5.4	50.114 3	-1.3	50.251 4	-1.08

as required with 3 : 1 mixture of toluene-methanol. Freshly prepared titrant was always used. Alcoholic potassium hydroxide was prepared by dissolving KOH in isopropanol. Titrants were standardised using standard benzoic acid solution in isopropanol. Stock solution containing 2.54 mg of HMDM per ml was prepared in acetone and different volumes of this solution (0.5–20.0 ml) were diluted to 20 ml to get the solution of different concentration.

A Systronics 304 conductometer was used for conductometric titration. The potential measurements were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ with a Systronics 335 pH meter. Glass electrode as reference and antimony/antimony oxide electrode were used as indicator electrode.

Procedure : All titration were carried in nitrogen atmosphere in triplicate in acetone medium.

Enthalpimetric titration : A 2 ml solution of required concentration of HMDM was titrated in inert N_2 -atmosphere by continuous addition of titrant ($t\text{-Bu}_4\text{NOH}$ and alcoholic KOH) with stirring and temperature was recorded for every 0.2 ml addition. Near the end-point, temperature was recorded for every 0.02 ml addition. It was seen that as a titrant was added the temperature decreased slightly till the end-point and at the end-point the curve showed

sudden break with sharp rise in temperature due to dimerisation of acetone for which excess base act as catalyst. End-point was determined from the graph (volume of base vs temperature) by extrapolation. End-points for standard benzoic acid and blank were determined in the same way.

Methods for conductometric and potentiometric titrations were as usual and the end-point was determined graphically.

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